

XILOGEL® AND XILOGEL® HS

FOR INTENSE SKIN MOISTURIZATION

CHARACTERISTICS

XILOGEL®	XILOGEL® HS	AVAILABLE DOCUMENTATION
HPLC content of Xyloglucan: 85 - 102% Form: white yellow powder Stability: retesting date 2 years Level of use: 0.1- 2% Dynamic viscosity (C=2, 100 rpm): 800 - 2500 cps Solubility (C=2, water, 100 rpm): clear or slightly opalescent solution	HPLC content of Xyloglucan: ≥ 75% Form: white yellow powder Stability: retesting date 2 years Level of use: 0.1- 2% Dynamic viscosity (C=2, 100 rpm): 500 - 2000 cps Solubility (C=2, water, 100 rpm): clear or slightly opalescent solution	Botanical Certificate Method of analysis Reference Standards Safety Data Sheet Published Literature Confidential documentation Cosmos validation (Xilogel®)

SAFETY DATA*

- The use of Xilogel® and Xilogel® HS in the tests performed showed it is devoid of side effects.
- Additionally, it resulted not irritant for the skin¹ nor the eye,^{2,3} not phototoxic⁴, not sensitizer^{5,6} nor mutagenic⁷ and to be considered safe when used in the customary or expected way.

FORMULATION EXAMPLES

AFTER SHAVE SERUM WITH XILOGEL®		INTENSE MOIST SERUM WITH XILOGEL® HS		Formulation Advice
Aqua (water)	85.60%	Aqua (water)	94.40%	
Xilogel®	0.50%	Xilogel® HS	1.00%	
Imidazolydinyl urea	0.30%	Carbomer	0.50%	
Disodium EDTA	0.10%	Witch hazel water	3.00%	
Glycerin	4.00%	Water / Glucose / Sorbitol / Sodium Glutamate / Urea / Sodium PCA / Glycine / Lactic Acid / Hydrolyzed Wheat protein / Panthenol	1.00%	
Ginkgo biloba Terpenes Phytosome®	1.00%	Preservatives	0.10%	
Sericoside Phytosome®	0.50%	XILOGEL® HS IS RECOMMENDED FOR: Clear gels High concentration clear serums Skin care and Body care formulation XILOGEL® IS RECOMMENDED FOR: Skin care and Body care They are both compatible in various systems, from traditional to silicon emulsions to even almost anhydrous systems as lipstick.		
Centerox®	1.00%			
Sodium hyaluronate	0.05%			
Polysorbate 20	1.00%			
Phenoxyethanol	0.80%			
Sodium polyacrylate / Dimethicone / Ciclopentasiloxane / Trideceth-6 / PEG / PPG 18 /18 Dimethicone	5.00%			
Parfum (fragrance)	1.50%			

* All safety trials are compliant to EU regulation 1223/2009.

The ingredients described herein are offered for consideration for use in personal care products. The information provided describes historical use, ingredient activity and other information that may be relevant to their use in such products. How each ingredient would contribute to a particular product would be formulation specific. Furthermore please note that this documentation is available for various countries all over the world and hence it may contain statements not applicable to your country.

CLINICAL EFFICACY OF XILOGEL® ON SKIN HYDRATION

- A single blind, benchmark controlled clinical study has been conducted on 20 volunteers aged 35-60.⁸ The duration of the study was four weeks, with each volunteer being its own control (half face treated with each formulation). Two simple formulations, one containing Xilogel® at 0.5% and the other the positive benchmark at the same concentration (Sodium Hyaluronate, MW 1.1 - 1.7 mio Da), were applied on each half face.
- Preliminary measurements of short term skin hydration were collected at 30' from the first application. Long term hydration was evaluated after four weeks of use twice daily. Other skin parameters have been assessed as well, i. e. skin elasticity, skin roughness and skin density.
- Xilogel® induced an immediate increase in skin hydration by 59.2% ($p < 0.05$), an improvement in skin moist higher than the one induced by the positive reference Sodium Hyaluronate with a statistically significant difference between the two.
- Xilogel® also induced a significant improvement in overall elasticity (R2 parameter, Cutometer), a decrease in skin roughness with the average roughness parameter decreasing by 27.6% ($p < 0.001$) and the maximum roughness parameter decreasing by 21.3% ($p < 0.001$). Finally, Xilogel® induced an improvement in skin density (by echogenicity) by 7.9% ($p < 0.05$), comparable to the performances of the positive benchmark.

Effect of Xilogel® on crow feet area (wrinkle depth)

HYDRATION EFFICACY OF XILOGEL® AND XILOGEL® HS

- Xilogel® and Xilogel® HS have been compared to betaglucan as another positive benchmark for skin hydration.⁹ The study was conducted on 20 volunteers and two concentrations of all actives were evaluated (0.5 and 1%). Short term hydration has been evaluated at 30', 1 and 2 h from product application. Both Xilogel® and Xilogel® HS overperformed betaglucan and all formulations were statistically significantly more hydrating compared to the placebo control. Specifically at the lowest concentration tested (0.5%), Xilogel® HS improved skin hydration by 47% at T30, Xilogel® by 49% and betaglucan by 41.2%. At the highest tested concentration (1%), Xilogel® HS improved skin hydration by 50%, Xilogel® by 48.8% and betaglucan by 43% ($p < 0.001$ all actives). No remarkable differences have been observed between Xilogel® and Xilogel® HS.

IN VITRO INHIBITION OF MARKERS OF AGEING

- The activity of β -galactosidase, considered as a marker of ageing in the Hayflick model, has been evaluated on aged keratinocytes and expressed as arbitrary fluorescence units.¹⁰ β -galactosidase is a lysosomal enzyme expressed both in aged and non-aged cells, but its activity is only evident in aged keratinocytes and fibroblasts. Xilogel®, at three different concentrations (0.2%, 0.5%, 1%), has decreased the activity of β -galactosidase by 21%. In a different model,¹¹ the expression of filaggrin has been evaluated by immunochemistry using a monoclonal anti-filaggrin antibody and a secondary fluorescent antibody. Filaggrin expression has shown a tendential increase, in line with the clinical observations.

DID YOU KNOW...

- The seed of Tamarind has a high content of polysaccharides. The main component, constituting Xilogel® and Xilogel® HS, is a branched polysaccharide of a cellulose-type backbone (β -[1-4]D-glucose which carries xylose and galactose constituents.¹² The Tamarind tree is considered as one of the most beautiful tropical trees and it is used both for nutritional purposes and also for manufacturing spices.

TRADE NAME	INCI (PCPC)	INCI (EU)	EC NUMBER	CAS N.	INDENA CODE
Xilogel®	Tamarindus indica Seed Polysaccharide	Tamarindus indica Seed Polysaccharide	254 - 442 - 6	39386 - 78 - 2	9070100
Xilogel® HS	Tamarindus indica Seed Polysaccharide	Tamarindus indica Seed Polysaccharide	254 - 442 - 6	39386 - 78 - 2	9070130

1. Indena data on file, RTC report 87330, 2012, 2014. - 2. Indena data on file, Bioservice report 114914, 2011. - 3. Indena, data on file, RTC report 87320, 2012. - 4. Indena, data on file, Bioservice report 114915, 2011. - 5. Indena, data on file, Vitroscreen report 42-12, 2012. - 6. Indena, data on file, Consumer Product Testing report C12-5703.01, 2013. - 7. Indena data on file, Bioservice report 114916, 2011. - 8. "Tamarindus indica Xyloglucan" Maramaldi G, *Cosmetic Technology*, vol 14(5), pag 17-21, 2011. - 9. Indena, data on file, ISPE report 205/14/01-07, 2014. - 10. Indena, data on file, Bioalternatives report GT110234, 2011. - 11. Indena, data on file, Bioalternatives report GT110233, 2011. - 12. "Gelation of tamarind seed polysaccharide in the presence of ethanol", Yamanaka S. et al, *Food Hydrocolloids* 14, pag 125-128, 2000.

